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1 Executive summary

This report presents a status and progress report on current developments in the ICT e-infrastructures relevant to the biomedical research infrastructures participating in the BioMedBridges project and includes a number of observations and recommendations from the project's e-infrastructure Advisory Board.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Collation of e-infrastructure requirements from ESFRI BMS projects to identify areas of common interest.	x	
2	Collation of requirements for data and service bridges from BioMedBridges work packages.		X
3	Acting as a focus for the communication of updates on e-infrastructure technology developments to partners.	X	
4	Reporting on the status of ICT e-infrastructures from the viewpoint of the ESFRI BMS projects.	x	
5	Making technical recommendations on current and potential e-infrastructure technologies.	x	

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Introduction

This report provides an update of the current status of the pan-European e-infrastructures for academic research and their current activities relevant to the biomedical sciences research infrastructures (BMS RIs) involved in BioMedBridges.

As described in the previous report, it is useful to look at e-infrastructure as a layered model, with the layers representing:

1. Computer Networking
2. Computing
3. Data storage and Management
4. User tools (VRC = Virtual Research Communities and Virtual Research Environment).

Layer 4 is represented by community-centred projects like BioMedBridges and probably represents the most straightforward opportunities for collaborative developments between e-infrastructures and biomedical research communities; however, here we will continue to focus on opportunities in layers 1-3.

3.2 Review of progress

3.2.1 Recommendations and questions raised in the first periodic report

Point 1: Each BMS RI needs a formal e-infrastructure contact

Over the first two years of the project it became apparent that there was a need for a “technical interface” between each BMS RI and the e-infrastructure advisory board. To address this, the Board asked for the RIs to appoint a

formal contact person. The BMS RI followed this request and BioMedBridges organised an interactive workshop for these contacts to get together with e-infrastructures representatives (see Point 3).

There are two further important routes of communication that do not preclude individual contacts between the RIs and the e-infrastructure providers:

- As the focus of BioMedBridges is to work across the BMS RIs to improve data interoperability and integration, the project facilitates the interaction between BMS RIs and e-infrastructures, identifying and communicating the needs across the entire community.
- Since the e-infrastructures are basically a network of national centres, a path for concrete action is between the national node and the respective node for any of the BMS infrastructures in the relevant country.

Point 2: We encourage interaction with other cluster projects

The collaboration of the four cluster projects funded under FP7 (BioMedBridges, DASISH, CRISP and ENVRI) culminated in a working paper on common challenges published in early 2014¹. The paper identifies common challenges in data management, sharing and integration across biomedical sciences, physics, social science and humanities, and environmental sciences. Strikingly, almost all of the sixteen identified topics apply to all four disciplines: only two (semantics and semantic interoperability) apply to all four except physics and one (dynamic data management) to all except physics and biomedical sciences.

The other three cluster projects have now concluded or are nearing their end. As far as possible, the established collaboration on developing solutions to

¹ Field, Laurence et al. (2013) Realising the full potential of research data: common challenges in data management, sharing and integration across scientific disciplines. ZENODO. [10.5281/zenodo.7636](https://zenodo.org/record/105281)

common, “generic” needs should continue by engagement between any follow-up cluster projects funded under INFRADEV-4. In addition, any projects funded under INFRADEV-3 are expected to provide further opportunities for focused joint work between e-infrastructures and BMS RIs.

Point 3: There is a variable depth in understanding of e-infrastructure requirements across the BMS RI; in many cases we are yet to see the real requirements emerging

It is clear that the work done in the BioMedBridges project will assist the BMS RIs in understanding and identifying their e-infrastructure requirements and help to ensure that the needs are aligned across all BMS RIs as far as this is possible and useful. Contributing to this and based on the suggestion made by the e-infrastructure advisory board, a workshop of BMS RI technical representatives with e-infrastructures (“Preparing for the data deluge” held on 15-16 May 2014 in Hinxton) highlighted the current challenges. As part of the workshop report², participants produced a comprehensive “big data checklist” to collect the information that is relevant in communication and negotiations with e-infrastructures (see Annex 1 to this document).

In summary, it is still difficult for some RIs to identify their data-related requirements. However, this is not unexpected due to the different stages of development of some of the RIs. Even RIs that are advanced or very advanced with respect to defining their/their communities’ data-related requirements necessarily need to go through a period of defining specific needs as their priorities for the coming years are set.

It is clear that general knowledge of and about e-infrastructure solutions is also needed by the non-technical RI support staff, such as the project managers, to aide communication, networking and collaboration. The BioMedBridges knowledge exchange workshop on “Data strategies for research

² REPORT: BioMedBridges workshop on e-infrastructure support for the life sciences – Preparing for the data deluge. ZENODO. [10.5281/zenodo.13942](https://zenodo.org/record/105281)

infrastructures”³ that is being organised to take place on 19 February in Munich will contribute to addressing this by providing relevant information to project managers.

BioMedBridges, as well as some of the individual BMS RIs, has also engaged with the Research Data Alliance RIs (e.g. the Structural Biology IG⁴ or ELIXIR Bridging Force IG⁵). These activities can also help in understanding data-related requirements, and their particular unique or generic aspects, ultimately aiding the dialogue with the e-infrastructures.

Point 4: E-infrastructure providers need to know what the current ICT “pain points” are for the BMS research infrastructures (i.e. what aspects of ICT currently cause problems?)

One of the ICT pain points in the life sciences that is clear is access to capacity compute and storage, co-located with the major reference datasets and with on-demand access to key reference data. Another pain point is the lack of support services for life science projects – services that reside on top of the e-infrastructures – such as, for example, for the secure handling of and collaboration with personalised medicine data.

Following from the previous point, understanding how to address these requires further refinement of the specific needs and is likely best tested in smaller pilot studies. Pilot studies provide a route to establishing collaborations, give an insight into priorities, and help to identify and better understand technical challenges. A related pilot project has been launched by the EGI and ELIXIR communities in December 2014 to improve support for the replication, discovery and usage of life-science reference datasets. The project receives contributions from several NGIs, ELIXIR nodes, and e-infrastructure

³ <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-data-strategies-research-infrastructures>

⁴ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/structural-biology-ig.html>

⁵ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/elixir-bridging-force-ig.html>

as well as life science experts beyond these structured communities. The planned length of the pilot is 9 months. Further details about the project are provided in Annex 2.

3.3 Developments in the current European e-infrastructure relevant to the life sciences

3.3.1 Networking

The model for research and education networking in Europe is of a single national entity per country (the National Research and Education Network – NREN) connecting to a common pan-European backbone infrastructure. In combination these networks provide a powerful tool for international collaborative research projects – particularly those with demanding data transport requirements. NRENs are able to connect individual sites to their high-bandwidth infrastructures or arrange point-to-point services for bilateral collaborations. GÉANT provides a single point of contact to coordinate the design, implementation and management of network solutions across the NREN and GÉANT domains.

3.3.1.1 Network Technology

The GÉANT network (like the majority of NRENs) has a hybrid structure – operating a dark-fibre network and transmission equipment wherever possible and leasing wavelengths from local suppliers in more challenging regions. This structure allows the operation of both IP and point-to-point services on a common footprint.

At the time of writing (April 2013) GÉANT is in the final stages of a migration to a new generation of both transmission and routing equipment platforms. The resulting network will see a significant increase in the bandwidth available along with an improved range of network services. GÉANT's pre-provisioned capacity on each of the core network trunks (covering western and central Europe) will be 500Gbps and an advanced routing/switching platform will

deliver IP, VPN and point-to-point services with greater flexibility to all European NRENs.

3.3.1.2 Network Service Developments

The GÉANT project provides more than just a physical network infrastructure. Its service development and research activities address directly the needs of the R&E community both by providing advanced international services on the NREN and GÉANT backbones, and also by developing software and middleware to target network-related issues from campus to global environments.

Services particularly relevant to Biological sciences include:

- GÉANT IP – a high quality, flexible IP service providing robustness and high levels of availability, high-bandwidth and global reach. This service provides the highest quality internet access to European and Global academic and research establishments. The vast majority of R&E sites in Europe access this service automatically through their local NREN connection.
- GÉANT point-to-point services (Plus, Lambda and VPN) –offer guaranteed routing, latency and stability on the GÉANT footprint and through global partnerships, to other world regions. These services are particularly suitable for close collaboration between a well-defined set of participating institutions.
- These GEANT network services may be enhanced by the use of network monitoring tools (perfSONAR). Coordination and design of multi-domain solutions can be provided by GÉANT user support.
- eduROAM allows users to access Wifi networks seamlessly across different institutions around the world, using the same login credentials. eduROAM implementations are extremely widespread globally including at leading Bioscience institutions such as EBI.
- eduGAIN addresses the need for digital identity to be recognised across national borders. National identity federations link the service

providers and the institutional identity providers in each country, but for secure international access to databases and other resources, eduGAIN enables a single sign on. This service is being tested in the context of ELIXIR.

Services under development in GÉANT include:

- Software-defined networking to facilitate faster and easier network configuration.
- A cloud brokerage service to facilitate easier adoption of cloud services from the commercial and community cloud sectors. Federation-as-a-service: providing a set of tools that allow a organisation to establish their own identity federation. It will also possible for GÉANT to provide a managed identity federation service –details on request.
- For full details of GÉANT services see www.geant.net/services.

3.3.1.3 Service Availability

GÉANT operates an infrastructure connecting NRENs in the vast majority of countries across Europe. These NRENs each have extensive national infrastructure and provide connections to universities, research centres and other not-for-profit institutions. A full list of GÉANT NRENs can be found at www.geant.net/About/partners.

In addition to its pan-European reach, the GÉANT network has extensive links to networks in other world regions including North America, Latin America, the Caribbean, North Africa and the Middle East, Southern and Eastern Africa, the South Caucasus, Central Asia and the Asia-Pacific Region. In addition, there is on-going work to connect to Western and Central Africa.

A full list of countries that interconnect with GÉANT can be found at <http://www.geant.net/Network/Global-Connectivity>.

To establish connectivity to GÉANT, institutions should contact their local NREN. For international collaboration, GÉANT can help with design and coordination of solutions involving multiple NREN networks.

3.3.2 Computing

3.3.2.1 PRACE

PRACE (<http://www.prace-ri.eu>) provides high-end computing resources to European top science. The largest 3 to 4 PRACE systems are generally referred to as “tier-0”. These systems are in general significantly larger than other European computer systems accessible to researchers and they have a policy of allocating resources for European usage based on a peer review system. The resources are accessible to applicants with successful proposals submitted in response to Calls for Proposals. The "Guide for Applicants to Tier-0 Resources" on the PRACE website (<http://www.prace-ri.eu/HPC-access>) provides detailed information on preparing applications and the peer review process that follows the submission. Post Award obligations include a final report and acknowledgement of PRACE support. PRACE publishes Calls for Proposals in February and in September. Preparatory access proposals, allowing users to develop software or test out novel ideas, are accepted at any time, with access granted on a quarterly basis.

The first phase of PRACE will end in mid-2015, after which PRACE 2.0 (Horizon 2020) will start, subject to confirmation of funding. In addition to providing access to very large Tier-0 HPC resources, PRACE also pools some national-level (Tier-1) resources and makes them available through specific calls. The availability of the Tier-1 resources for European use is also subject to funding being made available.

PRACE implementation projects include a range of activities that are likely to be interesting for the biological and medical science communities: training courses, software development, technology tracking and access to prototype resources. Three implementation projects have already been carried out (PRACE 1IP-3IP) and the fourth (PRACE 4IP) was submitted in September 2014, with the results expected in early 2015. If the proposal is successful, PRACE 4IP can contribute to the biomedical application development, training needs and data intensive computing requirements, to name a few examples.

It is important to note that the explosion in the data generation capacity of scientific equipment and sensors is creating a new class of researchers who have different demands in terms of their use of computing power and of how and where their data is stored. Traditionally, users needed PRACE to develop tools to generate data, for modelling and simulations, which had to be kept to compare with other models. In contrast, the new type of users wants to analyse data generated elsewhere and tends not to have a strong background in computing. It is important to understand these users' requirements, in particular concerning how the data will be used, preserved and stored in the long-term.

3.3.2.3 Exascale Initiatives

Most of these initiatives have just ended or are about to end. The current Horizon 2020 program is expected to launch new projects, for example Centers of Excellence (with software focus) projects (call Jan 2015), Virtual Research Environments (call Jan 2015) and some others.

The development towards extreme computing and computing systems has a central place in the European Commission's Horizon 2020 innovation and research program. For example, specific calls "Towards Exascale High Performance Computing" have been announced in the Future and Emerging Technologies program.

The European Technology platform for HPC (ETP4HPC)⁶ is maybe the community body that most intensively, and in collaboration with the EC, drives the agenda for exascale computing in Europe. EESI-2⁷, the second of two EC projects that has focussed on exascale software, will come to an end at the beginning of 2015. The project is also collaborating with a similar US initiative and together they have started a series of workshops under the title "Big Data

⁶ <http://www.etp4hpc.eu/>

⁷ <http://www.eesi-project.eu/pages/menu/homepage.php>

and Extreme Scale Computing”⁸. Other tracks in H2020 and especially the “Future and Emerging Technologies” part of the program are focusing on the longer-term perspective, including extreme miniaturisation and quantum computing. It is not yet evident which parts of exascale work will be relevant to BMS RIs.

3.3.2.4 European Grid Infrastructure

The European Grid Infrastructure (EGI; <http://www.egi.eu/>) is a collaboration of computing resource providers that delivers integrated computing services to European researchers. The infrastructure is a publicly funded e-infrastructure which provides European scientists access to more than 370,000 logical CPUs, 180 PB of disk space, 167 PB of tape space and data. More than 1.7 M compute jobs are processed every day in EGI.

EGI supports computing (including closely coupled parallel computing normally associated with HPC), compute workload management services, data access and transfer, data catalogues, storage resource management, and other core services such as user authentication, authorisation and information discovery that enable other activities to flourish. Resources are provided by over 350 resource centres that are distributed across 56 countries in Europe, the Asia-Pacific region, Canada, and Latin America. EGI services remove the need for research communities to develop and operate their own bespoke services, but rather to benefit from experience across a range of user communities.

User communities gain access to EGI services by partnering with EGI, either directly through federating their own resource centres, or indirectly by accessing national or regional resource centres that already support their communities. The funding support for access varies widely across the federation.

⁸ <http://www.exascale.org/bdec/>

During the last 12 months EGI matured its portfolio of solutions that help accelerate data-intensive research. The most relevant developments in EGI for BMS infrastructures during the reporting period were:

1. Launch of EGI Federated Cloud

After nearly two years of development the EGI community opened the 'EGI Federated Cloud' as a production infrastructure in May 2014. The new infrastructure⁹ is based on open standards and offers unprecedented versatility and cloud services tailored for European researchers. It is a connected grid of institutional clouds built around open standards. With the EGI Federated Cloud, researchers and research communities can:

- Deploy scientific applications and tools onto remote servers (in the form of Virtual Machine images)
- Store files, complete file systems or databases on remote servers
- Use compute and storage resources elastically based on dynamic needs (scale up and down on-demand)
- Immediately address workloads interactively (no more waiting time as with grid batch jobs)
- Access resource capacity in 19 institutional clouds (the number is growing, see up to date values at https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Fedcloud-f:ResourceProviders#Fully_integrated_Resource_Providers)
- Connect their own clouds into a European network to integrate and share capacity, or build their own federated cloud with the open standards and technologies used by the EGI Federated Cloud.

Since its launch, the EGI Federated Cloud has attracted more than 35 use cases¹⁰ from various scientific projects, research teams and communities. Among these there are several applications from biological sciences:

⁹ EGI Federated Cloud: <http://go.egi.eu/cloud>

¹⁰ Use cases of the EGI federated cloud: https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Federated_Cloud_Communities

- READemption: RNA-sequence analysis of data to understand different biological features and behaviour
- OpenModeller: The Ecological Niche Modelling (ENM) Workflow takes as input a file containing species occurrence points to create a model with the OpenModeller Web Service
- RSAT (Regulatory Sequence Analysis Tools): provides a series of modular computer programs specifically designed for the detection of regulatory signals in non-coding sequences
- BILS portal: front-end to biological tools for users without significant IT skills
- PConsC2: tools for protein structure prediction
- Genome Annotation service: genome browser to run genome annotation pipeline
- EDIT: a portal to access/visualize Catalogue of Life taxonomy data
- Chipster: a user-friendly analysis software for high-throughput data with over 300 analysis tools for NGS, microarray, proteomics and sequence applications
- VirtualCing, a Virtual Machine providing proof-of-concept demonstration of the validation and improvement of biomolecular NMR structures

2. Integrating ELIXIR reference datasets within the European Grid Infrastructure project

Significant work has been done by EGI in the past to help the deployment and discovery of services, where “services” can be either computationally oriented (such as batch queues) or application oriented (such as web services, ready-to-use applications embedded in portal gateways or encapsulated in Virtual Machine Images). However, in bioinformatics many services used for analyses rely on public reference datasets. Reference datasets are getting big and users struggle to discover, download and compute with them. Recognising the need to work with reference datasets, EGI and ELIXIR defined and launched a pilot project in December 2014. The pilot will facilitate the discovery of existing

reference datasets in EGI and will develop and deploy services that allow the replication of life-science reference datasets by data providers, resource providers and researchers, and ease the use of these datasets by life science researchers within analysis applications. The pilot is expected to run for 9 months; further information about the project can be found in Annex 2 and at https://wiki.eqi.eu/wiki/Integrating_Reference_Datasets.

3. Simplifying access to EGI for the ‘long tail of science’

While processes to gain access to EGI are well established across the NGIs for entire user communities, individual researchers and small research teams sometimes struggle to access compute and storage resources from the network of NGIs for the implementation of ‘big data applications’. Recognising the need for simpler and harmonised access for individual researchers and small research groups, i.e. the ‘long tail of science’, the EGI community started to design and prototype a new platform in October 2014. The platform will provide integrated services from the NGIs to those researchers and small research teams who work with large data but have limited or no expertise in using distributed systems. The platform will lower the barrier to access grid and cloud infrastructure via a centrally operated access management portal and an open set of virtual research environments designed for the most frequent use cases. The project defines security policies and implements new security services that enable personalised, secure and yet simple access to e-infrastructure resources via the virtual research environments for individual users. The platform will authenticate users via the EduGAIN federation and other username–password based mechanisms, complementing the long established certificate-based access mechanisms. The prototype system is planned to be available in March 2015 and a production system will be established based on this by the EGI-Engage project. Further information about the pilot project is available at https://wiki.eqi.eu/wiki/Long-tail_of_science_pilot.

4. Integrating EGI Applications Database with EMBL-EBI identity provider

The EGI Applications Database (AppDB) is a registry of software tools and frameworks, scientific applications, and Virtual Machine Images that are available for users on EGI sites (grid and cloud). In order to simplify access to the AppDB service for life-science communities, the authentication system of AppDB has been expanded with support for the EduGAIN federation and particularly with the EMBL-EBI identity provider from EduGAIN¹¹. Because of this extension, users with an account from EMBL-EBI can directly login to the AppDB service to register new entries and to browse and view protected items of their communities. The work aims to serve as a demonstrator for the EBI technical team and for the broader life-science community of how access to EGI's marketplace services, the EGI AppDB, can be provided to institutional users via EduGAIN. EGI is committed to work with the biomedical sciences research infrastructures involved in BioMedBridges and add their institutional identity provider into the EGI AppDB service upon request.

5. End of EGI-InSPIRE, start of EGI-Engage

EGI's first nearly 5 years were supported by the 'EGI-Integrated Sustainable Pan-European Infrastructure for Research in Europe' (EGI-InSPIRE) FP7 project. EGI-InSPIRE came to an end in December 2014. A new initiative, EGI-Engage was recently funded by the European Commission for support under the H2020 framework programme. EGI-Engage will launch in March 2015 with a total budget of 8.7 million Euros for 2.5 years.

One of the main objectives of EGI-Engage is to expand the capabilities of EGI (e.g. cloud and data services) and the spectrum of its user base by engaging with large Research Infrastructures (RIs), the long tail of science, and with industry/SMEs. The key engagement instrument for this will be a network of eight Competence Centres, in which National Grid Initiatives (NGIs), user communities, technology and service providers will join forces to collect requirements, integrate community-specific applications into state-of-the-art

¹¹ <http://appdb.egi.eu>

services, foster interoperability across e-infrastructures, and evolve services through a user-centric development model. The competence centres will provide state-of-the-art services, training, technical user support and application co-development to specific scientific domains. The following life science (or closely related) communities will have dedicated Competence Centres in EGI-Engage:

- 1) Biobanking and medical research (Biobanking and Biomolecular Research Infrastructure, BBMRI-ERIC),
- 2) Life-science research (ELIXIR)
- 3) Structural biology and brain imaging research (MoBrain supporting WeNMR and Integrating Structural Biology – INSTRUCT)
- 4) Biodiversity and ecosystem research (LifeWatch)

3.3.2.5 Helix Nebula Marketplace

The stimulus provided by publicly funded research organisations (CERN, EMBL and ESA) via the Helix Nebula initiative has led to the creation of its first product: the *Helix Nebula Marketplace* (HNX¹²) with considerable investment by the commercial cloud service providers and the active engagement of the publicly funded European e-infrastructures GÉANT and EGI.

HNX is still in its early phase but has already shown the value of such public-private partnerships where, driven by the common procurement needs of research organisations, Europe's IT industry has shown it is willing to invest. The demand-side has continued its deployment testing and procurement activities with the Helix Nebula Marketplace (HNX) product during 2014. With approximately 30% of its membership being SMEs, the Helix Nebula initiative is providing a channel by which innovative cloud service companies can work with major IT companies and public research organisations. Helix Nebula has published an update to the strategic plan¹³ that launched the initiative three

¹² <http://hnx.helix-nebula.eu>

¹³ <http://www.helix-nebula.eu/publications/deliverables/d92-strategic-plan-scientific-cloud-computing-infrastructure-europe-three>

years ago and a roadmap for future developments¹⁴. The intention is to spread the scope of the Helix Nebula initiative to become a forum between the supply-side and the demand-side where issues of common interest (such as procurement models, contractual frameworks, service platforms etc.) can be addressed.

The rate of adoption of open source cloud software stacks, in particular OpenStack, means they are rapidly becoming de-facto standards in both the enterprise and public sector domains. EGI has continued to develop the prototype EGI Fed Cloud¹⁵ ([see previous section](#)) which has been tested with several user communities and integrated into HNX. The integration has been tested with flagship applications from CERN and ESA. The experience gained from this work has shown that integrating publicly funded e-infrastructures with commercial services to provide a combined platform on which to build new services has a clear value for users. Two developments would provide the basis for further integration:

1. A common catalogue of services including services provided by all suppliers present in the exchange
2. A federated identity management system offering a single sign-on facility to access services across all suppliers.

The provision of services via supplier-funded resources is the foundation of national and European e-infrastructures. The concept of a marketplace with the ability for users to choose from a range of services and suppliers can offer a practical implementation of the concept of an e-infrastructure commons. The exchange approach coupled with the pay-per-use model, as championed by Helix Nebula, is being considered by a number of e-infrastructures.

Through the work of initiatives such as Helix Nebula it has become clear that it is essential to separate the roles of *end-user* (the researcher making use of

¹⁴ <http://www.helix-nebula.eu/publications/deliverables/d91-roadmap-of-future-developments>

¹⁵ <https://www.egi.eu/export/sites/egi/infrastructure/cloud/fedcloudflyer2.pdf>

the services) and *customer* (the organisation sponsoring the consumption of the services by the end-user) and ensure that services, both commercial and publicly funded, are offered *free at the point of use*.

Publicly funded e-infrastructures are investigating a new brokering role to facilitate access to commercial services for their user base. A key attraction of the brokerage role is that it offers a new revenue stream. While these business model innovations should be encouraged it is important that competition between brokers does not lead to renewed fragmentation of the e-infrastructure commons. An aspect of brokerage which is often underestimated by the publicly funded e-infrastructures is the necessary financial engagement and liability. Experienced financial brokers from utility markets could help ensure the good governance of the exchange and take on board some of the financial risks from users and suppliers to accelerate the expansion of the market.

3.4 Data

3.4.1 Research data

3.4.1.1 EUDAT

EUDAT is the largest pan-European data infrastructure initiative initiated under the EC FP7 programme and is set to move towards a sustainable research data infrastructure at the Horizon 2020.

EUDAT brings together a large consortium of 33 partners, including research communities, national data and high performance computing (HPC) centres, technology providers, and funding agencies from 14 countries. EUDAT aims to build a sustainable cross-disciplinary and cross-national data infrastructure that provides a set of shared services for accessing and preserving research data.

Currently, EUDAT is working with more than 30 scientific communities and has built a suite of five integrated services to assist them in resolving their grand challenges. In the Life Science domain, EUDAT is currently working with research communities such as ELIXIR, BBMRI, ECRIN, DiXa, and VPH. Covering both access and deposit, from informal data sharing to long-term archiving, and addressing identification, discoverability and computability of both long-tail and big data, EUDAT services aim to address the full lifecycle of research data.

The current suite of EUDAT B2 services are:

- **B2DROP**: a secure and trusted data exchange service for researchers and scientists to keep their research data **synchronized** and up-to-date and to **exchange** with other researchers. <https://b2drop.eudat.eu>
- **B2SHARE**: a user-friendly, reliable and trustworthy service for researchers and communities to **store** and **share** small-scale research data coming from diverse contexts. <https://b2share.eudat.eu>
- **B2SAFE**: a robust, safe and highly-available data management and replication service allowing community and departmental repositories to **replicate** and **preserve** their research data across EUDAT data nodes. <http://www.eudat.eu/b2safe>
- **B2STAGE**: a reliable, efficient, easy-to-use service to ship large amounts of research data between EUDAT data nodes and workspace areas of high-performance **computing** systems. <http://www.eudat.eu/b2stage>
- **B2FIND**: a simple, user-friendly **metadata catalogue** of research data collections stored in EUDAT data centers and other repositories allowing finding collections of scientific data quickly and easily, irrespective of their origin, discipline or community <https://b2find.eudat.eu>

The EUDAT project operates in a European landscape of developing or already existing data infrastructures. These research infrastructures already have developed solutions and tools for managing their data. The goal of

EUDAT is not to replace these infrastructures, but to support and enrich them by providing strong data infrastructure component and generic services on which they can rely to build up their data strategy. EUDAT's vision is to enable European researchers and practitioners from any research discipline to preserve, find, access, and process data in a trusted environment, as part of a Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI) conceived as a *network of collaborating, cooperating centres, combining the richness of numerous community-specific data repositories with the permanence and persistence of some of Europe's largest scientific data centres*. At the heart of the CDI is a network of distributed storage systems hosted at the major scientific data centres. Between them, these centres manage more than 100 PB of high-performance, online disk in support of European research, plus an even greater amount of near-line tape storage. EUDAT's strength lies in the connections between these centres, the resilience resulting from the geographically distributed network, and its ability to store research data right alongside some of the most powerful supercomputers in Europe.

According to the CDI model, two categories of users can be established:

- “**Internal users**” are those concerned with the management of community-specific data repositories. Internal users can join their repositories formally with the CDI network, instantly benefitting from the persistence and resilience offered by the EUDAT partner network. Internal users are interested in archiving, replicating, processing and cataloguing data on behalf of the research community they support.
- “**External users**” are those wishing to share data with colleagues or collaborators, or those wishing to discover and re-use data as part of their ongoing research. External users can be anybody – researchers (from academia or industry), citizen scientists, policy makers, and members of the public, i.e. anyone wanting to share or re-use European research data in simple, powerful ways. As a direct complement to the core technical services, EUDAT also provides a raft of “soft” services to countries, communities and research organizations

in the process of developing their data infrastructure. These include consultancy services, data project enabling and training on best practice, technology, policy, management and licensing for research data.

3.4.3 Research Data Alliance

Together, EUDAT and OpenAIRE are driving international cooperation in tackling issues around large-scale data infrastructures through the recently formed international Research Data Alliance (RDA). The RDA is an international collaboration including participants from all around the world. In addition to EUDAT and OpenAIRE, the EC and NSF are directly represented in RDA. In Europe, the work of the RDA is supported by the iCORDI RDA-Europe project (coordinator Hilary Hanahoe, Trust-IT, UKCSC Finland). The RDA aims to accelerate and facilitate research data sharing and exchange. The work of the RDA is primarily be undertaken through its [working groups](#). Participation in working groups, starting new working groups, and attendance at the twice-yearly plenary meetings is open to all.

3.4.4 Open Data Commons of EGI

EGI developed its 'Open Data Commons' vision inspired by the emerging open access policy in the European Research Area. The goal of open access it to ensure that research results are made available free of charge to end-users and that are reusable. Research results thus become a shared community resource (i.e., a commons). In order for this to happen, researchers need to change their own behaviours and they need to be supported with services that simplify the sharing of research results, their discovery and reuse. In the EGI-Engage project (starting in March 2015) EGI will develop the concept of a federated open research data platform, an innovative solution enabling to publish data, link to open access repositories, and offering easy integration into processing capabilities (e.g. EGI Federated Cloud). Furthermore, the federated cloud infrastructure, including existing publicly funded institutional cloud and expanding to commercial clouds, will

evolve to offer IaaS, PaaS and SaaS¹⁶ for specific communities, the long-tail of research and the industrial/SME sector. In collaboration with other e-infrastructures, services will be tailored to meet the needs of the long tail of research and their evolution will be driven by the requirements of the RIs on the ESFRI roadmap that participate in the EGI Engage project through Competence Centres.

3.4.2 Publications

3.4.2.1 OpenAIRE

The three main objectives of OpenAIRE are to:

- **build support structures** for researchers in depositing FP7 research publications through the establishment of the European Helpdesk and the outreach to all European member states through the operation and collaboration of **27 National Open Access Liaison Offices**;
- **establish and operate an electronic infrastructure** for handling peer-reviewed articles as well as other important forms of publications (pre-prints or conference publications). This is achieved through a portal that is the **gateway** to all user-level services offered by the established e-infrastructure, including access (search and browse) to scientific publications and other value-added functionality (post-authoring tools, monitoring tools through analysis of document and usage statistics);
- work with several subject communities to *explore* the requirements, practices, incentives, workflows, data models, and technologies to deposit, access, and otherwise **manipulate research datasets** of various forms in combination with research publications.

¹⁶ see for example http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cloud_computing for an explanation of IaaS, PaaS and SaaS

5 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

The delivery was slightly delayed based on the wish to include information on recent developments, including the outcomes of various key funding applications.

6 Adjustments made

No adjustments were made to the deliverable.

Background information

This deliverable relates to WP11; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP11 Title: Technology Watch
 Lead: Neil Geddes, STFC
 Participants: EMBL, EGI, CSC, DANTE

The Technology Watch task force will comprise technical experts from each of the three BioMedBridges work packages (WP 3, 4 & 5) plus senior advisers from the ICT e-infrastructures community. The task force will monitor relevant developments in e-infrastructures, providing information, reports and links through the BioMedBridges website. The task force will attend the AGM and then report to the management structure. They will provide advice on current developments at the cutting edge of e-science and identify developments relevant to the BMS infrastructures, which could be adopted as the project progresses. They will provide advice on technical problems of concern to the work packages and discuss relevant new developments identified by the e-Advisory Board members.

Work package number	WP11	Start date or starting event:	month 1
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Work package title	Technology Watch				
Activity Type	RTD				
Participant number	1: EMBL	4: STFC	17: EGI	18: CSC	21: DANTE
Person-months per participant	3	2	1	1	1
<p>Objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Technology Watch task force will bring together the technical experts of the BioMedBridges partners to monitor and report on developments by European ICT Infrastructures and e-infrastructures to provide advice for the project. 2. The Technology Watch task force will facilitate the adoption of e-infrastructure technologies by the BioMedBridges work packages. 3. The Technology Watch task force will communicate advice from the ICT Infrastructures and the e-infrastructures to the BioMedBridges partners. 					
<p>The Technology Watch task force will produce periodic reports on the status of e-infrastructures relevant to the progress of BioMedBridges work packages, including the technology requirements for use cases and recommendations for the adoption of new e-infrastructure technologies and standards.</p> <p>Key tasks include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collation of e-infrastructure requirements from ESFRI BMS projects to identify areas of common interest • Collation of requirements for data and service bridges from BioMedBridges work packages • Acting as a focus for the communication of updates on e-infrastructure technology developments to partners. • Reporting on the status of ICT e-infrastructures from the viewpoint of the ESFRI BMS projects • Making technical recommendations on current and potential 					

e-infrastructure technologies

An important source of information exchange will be the e-infrastructure Reflection Group, which was founded to define and recommend best practices for the pan-European electronic infrastructure efforts. It consists of official government delegates from all the EU countries. The e-IRG produces white papers, roadmaps and recommendations, and analyses the future foundations of the European Knowledge Society and the needs of ESFRI projects in each domain.

Common issues identified for ESFRI BMS projects in the latest e-IRG blue paper are:

- Ability to manage massive quantities of data being generated across Europe and continuously growing
- Access to a wide variety of databases which are regularly updated
- Dealing with patient data where secure data management is essential
- Ease of use via Single Sign-On facility
- Large-scale usage of grid and cloud computing (within individual ESFRI BMS projects)
- Education and training for e-infrastructure usage

The task force will work with the e-infrastructures Reflection Group by monitoring e-IRG reports and contacting e-IRG members for further information on e-infrastructures and technologies of interest.

Deliverables

No.	Name	Due month
D11.1	First periodic report on current developments in the ICT e-infrastructures	18
D11.2	Second periodic report	36
D11.3	Third periodic report	48

Annex 1: “Big data checklist” for life science research infrastructures

The BioMedBridges Knowledge Exchange Workshop “Preparing for the data deluge”, held on 15-16 May 2014 in Hinxton, brought together representatives of several e-infrastructures and the biomedical sciences research infrastructures (BMS RIs). Participants were asked to take a forward look five years into the future and anticipate the information that would need to be available in order for effective support to be provided to the life science research infrastructures. The following questions emerged concerning what BMS RIs need to address to define their requirements and be able to start a productive dialogue with e-infrastructure providers.

Core questions

- **Data storage, volume and access:** Where will data be stored, and what data will be stored? Who will access stored data and how often? How many simultaneous users? Will stored data be replicated (backup, remote sites)? Are there ways to rationalise/automate long-term data management/storage (e.g. automatic deletion after “embargo” period)?
- **Networking requirements:** what are the network requirements for moving data - from production sites, for storage, analysis etc.?
- **Data analysis/compute:** where will this be located?
- **Raw data:** what are the RI’s raw data processing requirements?
- **Cloud solutions:** If desired, what would be most suitable: commercial? academic? federation? scale of federation? who?
- **Data curation:** who will curate the data? Are the necessary experts available?
- **Open data:** will the data be open and accessible to the wider user community? Under what conditions? What will the level of openness be? Are there restrictions? What is the nature of the restrictions?
- **Data protection and security:** what are the requirements?

- **Data production:** where will data be produced? By whom? How much? What will the rate of production be?

Additional questions

- How can requirements be defined in a useful/understandable way? (What are the key questions that can be addressed with possible solutions?)
- How can the necessary expertise at or translation between data producers/archivists and infrastructure providers be ensured?
- How will information about data be managed and by whom (both scientific information and e-infrastructure-relevant information)?
- Research questions are unpredictable - how much flexibility is needed? (What data will be compared or analysed in future?)
- What technological change is necessary or desirable to accommodate growing/developing data needs? Can this be driven by RIs and e-infrastructures (e.g. RDF machines)
- Are there commonalities/synergies between different BMS RIs concerning data that can be exploited?
- Can life science RIs and e-infrastructures jointly influence funders and policy makers on these issues?

Annex 2: Project “Integrating ELIXIR reference datasets within the European Grid Infrastructure”

There has been significant work done in the EGI in the past to help the deployment and discovery of services, where “services” can be either computationally oriented (such as batch queues) or application oriented (such as web-services, ready-to-use applications embedded in portal gateways or encapsulated in Virtual Machine Images). However in bioinformatics many services used for analysis purposes rely on public reference datasets. Reference datasets are getting big and users struggle to discover, download and compute with them. There is an increasing demand to compute the data where the reference datasets are located. EGI members already host some biological reference datasets across the infrastructure, however currently EGI neither provides discovery capabilities for available datasets, nor provides guidelines for those who wish to use these datasets or would like to replicate additional datasets onto EGI sites. Recognising the need for this kind of support the EGI and ELIXIR communities defined and launched a project¹⁷ in December 2014. The project will facilitate the discovery of existing reference datasets in EGI and will develop and deploy services that allows the replication of life science reference datasets by data providers, resource providers and researchers, and also ease the use of these datasets by life science researchers within analysis applications. The project is expected to run for 9 months and includes the following tasks:

1. Identify existing life science datasets in EGI
2. Identify reference datasets for replication
3. EGI AppDB extension to a dataset registry

¹⁷ Project website: https://wiki.eqi.eu/wiki/Integrating_Reference_Datasets

4. Tools for data replication
5. Analysis tools to work with data replicas
6. Integration with ELIXIR Registry

The project will benefit ELIXIR and the broader life science community by establishing:

1. A set of tools and recommendations that would help ELIXIR members and partners
 - Achieve more balanced load on storage resources across their sites
 - Unload user analysis jobs from large centres to partner sites (with data replicas)
 - Perform data processing at national or home institute resources
2. A pilot infrastructure that includes
 - Key datasets for life science analysis workflows
 - Information about applications and tools that researchers can choose from to work with reference datasets
 - A registry that provides information for users about the reference datasets and about the tools that are available to interact with these data
3. A group of experts who can
 - Guide the setup of production infrastructures based on the pilot infrastructure
 - Themselves become providers in production systems.

The project will benefit EGI by:

- Capturing and documenting knowledge about tools, methods and solutions to replicate large datasets onto the e-infrastructures (grid, cloud).

- Producing tools and best practices that are reusable and relevant to other scientific domains (not only life sciences).
- Broadening EGI's scope from a compute infrastructure to a data infrastructure.
- Strengthening the social network between the EGI and ELIXIR communities.